

- [https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How to Create a MIMS](https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How_to_Create_a_MIMS)
- MIMS 2.51 - MESS0008: Induction vs. Deduction in MIMS

MESS 0024

MIMS 2.52 - Engineering the MIMS Philosophy into a P⁷ Resolution

Philosophæther - Physics - Principles - Power in a Plug-n-Play Platform

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ABSTRACT

In this philosophically syncretic MESSy, we see that the *P*, *F*, and *D* sounds are related to the *P*, *F*, and *L* powers, where the Lord (consciousness-seed) is connected to the *D* sound, both plasmaglyphically and mytho-theologically. Nevertheless, the need to pre-engineer the MIMS philosophy future necessitated an ORDA:INED standard, in this case a P⁷ resolution level. The goal: to make the philosophy as plug-n-play as “All Men are Created Equal” and “the pursuit of happiness”, or “the golden rule,” etc. We need this philosophy, furthermore to be ordinal-numerical *ready*, and two definitions of power, one from plasma-electromagnetic dynamics from earlier analysis, and one from the Magnetic Universe, are all united vis-a-vis the concept that Power = Work / Time. Lastly, discussions of the layers of the Force, in terms of the fibonacci view, that is a *dæthereal* examination of either a) the philosophæther (herein defined) and/or b) natural philosophæ (*physics*).

Keywords: Physics - Philosophy - Aether - Power - Force - God - Dao - Fortunes

Reverse-Forward Thinking

If one practices Dao 道家, ostensibly to achieve *the Tao* 道 (as the Victorians saw it), then perhaps one will consider the act of *wayfaring* 远行. Particularly: hiking. When one hikes, it will happen, on occasion, that one wishes to leave the blazed path, to experience Frost's cathartic and existential paradox. You are safe upon the well-trod path, but your soul craves the untrod. The untrod is more accurate in describing our experience in science. Although many do repeat classic experiments, frequently people prefer to have their ways found in new ideas or places as yet untrodden. But like any set of woods or natural region, it is completely possible that the natural circulation of motion (going to a destination, survival, and return from to safety) will be met with obstructions, pitfalls, and even danger. In such a situation one should consider revisiting one's steps, (going in reverse), in order to make progress (going forward). In terms of philosophy, dialectics, and progress, the author calls this Reverse-Forward thinking. It is only a natural result and needs considering due to the past history of forward-reverse thinking and action, which has resulted in a poisoned world, poisonous science, the religion of Scientism, etc. It's just a sad aspect of the bass-ackwards way humans behave and think that feelings come before logic, conclusions before investigation, results before data, consequences before actions. These are naturally untrue, as in unworkable situations. Nevertheless, they are natural to human nature. Nietzsche¹ and others (Kafka, Marx, et al) did not desire to destroy lives, they were just spouting their thoughts (negative, pessimistic, nihilistic bullshit though they were, onto paper, hoping that they would positively affect the world or at least empty the mind in an exegesistic-orgasm of thought-drivel. But the results are in: genocide and World War.

Few, save Sir Doyle's "Sherlock Holmes"² character, saw through this in the 1800s. But we shall save that for the next discussion. In this work, the author wishes to prove the *future* mimsical value of MIMS, proving the past, present, and future loop of a good philosophy³. To prove that the MIMS philosophy⁴ not only is a good MIMS, and not an anti-MIMS, it is necessary to mimsically design (pre-engineer) the resolution based upon previous standardizations, in order to engineer the future of the philosophy. To engineer it, one must visioneer it, and this involves an interface with the PPPC⁵.

Visualize that the entire Vision of your 3D→2D image collapse (as discussed in Aether Flexion Wave theory⁶, and originally Triple-Plane Theory⁷) is then collapsed to a single moment of time. Do we not then need a philosophy that enables:

- Maximal connection to the moment as a participle of reality - a virtual particle or Realion⁸?
- Maximal potential maximization of the aetheric essence of the moment, in terms of capitalization and 'capture' of that Realion
- Minimal propagation of outflow (karmic)⁹ or damaging consequences (ie, mitigation), to the Self, Qiji (complete human body and form, energetics and spiritual included)
- Ditto for others, and environment

¹ "God is dead." ... thankfully not!

² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sherlock-Holmes-Pioneer-in-Forensic-Science-1976713>

³ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims>

⁵ Potentiality-Possibility-Probability-Cloud Acronyms

⁶ MESS0017: AFW - Using Fisheye and Pinch lens to discern Pixelation Adaptation

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EP EMC

⁸ An *alchemical-like* visual expression of the crystalized or distilled moment, in a defined, quantized form, measurable with data and dæther, as a present - and **real** (quantifiable) - identity or construct. See: the Wu Zhu Pian

⁹ MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences

- Maximal benefit to others and Society, without sacrifice of personal liberty, health, or property (unwillingly)
- Maximal benefit to the Shi¹⁰
 - Potentially mutual empowerment, if possible
- Maximal power with minimal consequences (trappings) and temptations that lead to sin and/or destruction
- Maximal Potentiality for alternate courses (switches) with minimal effort to apply the changes of one's total energetic dynamism to match The Changes 易 of the Tao (yi-dao)
- Minimal Risk Profile across a full spectrum of PPC *quantum data-streams*¹¹, specifically the Present.

The P⁷ Resolution¹²

The Present provides layer 8. Power exists throughout the entire *P* power¹³, or it wouldn't be the *P* power, to begin with. But the ordinal number se7en is of incredibly important value mytho-historically, and just as the six divisions could not be avoided in the Unity of 5 and 8 layers discussion¹⁴. In particular, 7 is the number of L.U.C.K. (I region), meaning it is modular to the Aether¹⁵, and vice versa (as examined in previous MIMSy), Aether has much to say about the *fortunes* - literal, figurative, and health - of the subject interacting with it. This is contained within the Nei Yeh¹⁶, and in many modern sources, including MIMS work. The only difficulty is in *proving* with **data** evidence, a direct connection (1:1 or otherwise). The Chinese spoke of Tianyi - Heaven's Will¹⁷ - but where is the data? Nevermind that we have these two issues (the æther proof and the checklist above), we will, for the moment, assume the 1:1 ætheric involvement in fortune, and some ratio with gnosis and logos in L.U.C.K.; for simplicity a 1/3 involvement.

Philosophæther

From this perspective, one must consider what [Natural] Philosophæ will interface with, membranically or via Dougherty [quantum] "tunnels" (if this is how the membrane works), with the *P* power (the 8 Laws of physics or "Principles").

Therefore, the author introduces a specific MIMSical '*lubricant*' that will design this: the concept of **Philosophæther**. How do we define this concept? It appears to the author to be either/or:

- ❖ The philosophies of nature and physics, metaphysics, etc. pertaining to the Aether, and related concepts (mimsical or otherwise)
 - Which, in a MIMS framework, need to rest upon the bedrock of MIMS 1.0, upon the scientific method, the Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology, or upon other empiricism.
- ❖ Aetheric topics having to do with, or pertaining to philosophies that drive mankind's fortunes and/or luck, and ancillary forces of Karma, Destiny, Fate, and CHAOS.

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

¹¹ Literally, different parallel processes of the Causality "black box" for which we seem to see only one final, definitive, collapse or action. See: Quantum Computing.

¹² The D level in ORDA:INED MESS0007: The ORDA Standard

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

¹⁴ the numbers 7, 9, and 11 do not take a backseat to the more popular non-Fibonacci cousins: 4, 10, and 12

¹⁵ Meaning it alters and changes the aether.

¹⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652/>

¹⁷ 天命 "Mandate of Heaven."

- ❖ It may also, not coincidentally, have to do with the manner by which the 8 Laws interact with the 5 regional forces of life, and with scientific studies that affect our understanding of these and their field-relations with each other, within or between the fibonacci pressure veins; that may likely include the [D]æther Flexion Wave, which is postulated to be motivating the Yi-dao upon the 3D/samsaric experience.
 - These yi-dao/Changes (which accord with some karmic/dharmic 'Plan' aka God's Plan/Heaven's Will/Fate, etc.) will be genuflected within the PPPC, causing a positive or negative feedback loop, which has a cumulative effect upon the psyche (via confirmation bias, etc.)
 - This psychic effect is digital spirit, but there is also the physical AME results upon the neurochemistry and energetico systems:
 - Primo Vasculature¹⁸ (CDNs¹⁹, meridians, etc.)
 - Chemico-metabalo
 - Sensorial (5 or 8, doesn't matter)
 - Mechanico-kinetic (ie, musculoskeletal)

Physics

In other words, the P⁷ resolution rests upon, unsurprisingly, the scientific field of Physics. But not just any physics, but that which is embraced in a laboratory and empirical setting (rather than mathemagicks, or theory first, test later):

- ★ High energy Plasma Physics (HEPP)
- ★ Quantum electrodynamics (QED)
- ★ Quantum chromodynamics (QCD)
- ★ Classical electromagnetism (CEM)
- ★ New Electromagnetism/dynamism (NEM)/PEMD
- ★ Electrogeometerology (EGM)
- ★ Organic chemistry based biology (OCB)
- ★ Electrochemistry (EC)
- ★ Physics based Medicines
- ★ Stratego-chemical geology (SCG)
- ★ Condensates
- ★ Alternate plasmoid physics and plasma fusion
- ★ Superconductivity etc.
- ★ Thermal spectroscopy
- ★ Electron [density] microscopy
- ★ Nuclear fission physics & radiology
- ★ Signals and communications sciences
- ★ Physical Logistics & Gamification (PLG) within ORDA
 - Heavy, heavy data basis; rather than math theorems
- ★ Misc. empirically based minor sciences.

¹⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2005290113002082>

¹⁹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

This is how you get a *phoundation* for the *phuture*. You lay it, brick by brick, until this is solid, and unmovable; or at least only movable by the Divine, who placed it in the *phirmament*, to begin with.

“and upon this rock I will build my church, and all the powers of hell will not conquer it.” ~Matthew 16:18

Principles

Discussing *the* principles is not unrelated, mytho-historically to *having* principles. The Chinese didn't call it Yi-dao, they had Tian-yi, and then there was Dao-de. De 德 (duh) was a moral, inner, masculine power of Truth, with a cosmic pole motif integral to the plasmascript and ideogram, which is not unrelated to Zheng 正, which means true, correct, or upright. This analysis is elementary, and contained elsewhere. The point, Dear Watson, is that the De is a principled power, connected to Righteousness, or Values, etc. Discipline might as well be written Descipline, for the D sound in the “deep” was the sound of POWER of Heaven, and of the buckling of ground unwilling to move, and yet moved. How firm was it, if the hills could skip like lambs²⁰?

In fact, as the EGM series shows, especially GEO 2.2, not firm at all²¹. It is only a *membranic* temper located between the Spheres of Heaven and of Earth²², the former having all the visible power that *shocked* the world, and the latter actually having the more potential charge and voltage, and the more direct vicinity to the lives of people. But the disquiet created by the sound of Di - the Lord (L power) - and the “winds of **destruction**” (6 of them, symbolized by the X or ‘cross’ glyph²³, or the swastika, as it were) - was only matchable by the terror of “high carp floods”²⁴ and deluges²⁵, or the Plague of Darkness, which claimed 9/10 Hebrews in the days of Moshe²⁶.

So, too, must this MIMS philosophy be rooted not in the POS ways of valuelessness, materialism (rather than spiritual-materialism), short-sighted and greedy, but instead in the principles that kept the Sages and gurus lively and safe, over thousands of years, but with the warmth and friendliness of a family home. Of a neighborhood that cooks and celebrates holidays together. The philosophy must be rooted in **timelessness**. The obsession by the Relativitists of making space-time both real and the only effective æther, has poisoned cosmological astronomy (astrophysics, so misnomered!), and it must be ended, and quite soonly rather than later.

Power

In MESSy 14, the k-Gurvature was calculated with **simple** techniques²⁷, and used to replace the tired, but admirable Newton's equation for gravity. The distance in that calculation was ridiculously small, at the decaXmicro scale of 1.32×10^{-60} m! This blasted way past the Planck Length, to suggestions of precision refinement unheard of. Although R. Ashcroft's ‘colleague’ maintains values at 10^{-3000} , if it can be believed.

In MESSy 16, the same method was applied semi-relentlessly to the other Newtonian mechanical concepts, such as momentum, kinetic energy, potential energy, and power²⁸.

²⁰ “Psalm 114:4 (MSG) The mountains turned playful and skipped like rams, the hills frolicked like spring lambs.”

²¹ MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY

²² MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME

²³ https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

²⁴ Enki & The World Order

²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1

²⁶ And 2/3 of those 1/10 died in the crossing of the Red Sea!

²⁷ MESS0014: CRH - Gravity as Resonance and Conservation

²⁸ MESS0016: MOND2 - Newtonian Mechanics and Sound in an electrodynamical model

- (1) “Since power is $V \cdot I$, we can rework this to mean that Power is: $\frac{Ft}{QV}$ or Newton-seconds per keV (20)”
 (2) In philosophæther: Power is then **Force-time** over Potential Voltage (potentiality²⁹).

In the Axioms of Power, the author writes,

Rules of Power	Equations of Power
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Power flows along the curves and currents of the advantageous position (Shi), though it spikes towards opportunities and vacuums ➤ Power must be used, or lost, it refuses stagnant homeostasis ➤ Power peaks and ebbs; collects and dissipates ➤ After a power crescendo, negative power flow gives power in equal measure, almost instantly, and usually violently (“snapback”) ➤ Power attracts power; seeking power encourages those who seek power to seek thee out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Power = work over time ❖ Power = influence + energy * concentration ❖ Power = ambition + will + discipline - sacrifice ❖ Power = imagination + focus ❖ Power = momentum enhanced by velocity ❖ Power = leverage = torque = force by distance

Therefore, let us say that the concepts of power definitely depend upon work, and upon time, and therefore velocity, in which distance hinges upon the high-def resolution of the *k*-Gurvature. All the rest of the concepts can relay back to Gaussian curvature, to curl, divergence, RLC, and Force. The **F** power, of course being the most consummate power of all of them, and in *physics* (pronounced with the F sound), this means the Plasma-electromagnetic Force. This power (2 layer) generates the A power (3 layer), and then 2³→8 laws, while 2+3 = 5 *phases* of matter or, more rightly, AME (atomic-mass-energy).

★ Therefore, to understand Power, one needs the SOUND of the *F* Power - that is resonance - and since the PEMF = the Unified Aether Field, we see that if Power, is work over time³⁰ as in Force within a change-flux density-field (perceived as time according to Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis³¹), then we can define power, *philosophically*:

(3) $Power = \frac{Force [keV]}{Field [m^3]} = \frac{Unified\ Aether\ [\text{æthons}]}{Plasma \times Electromagnetism\ [realions]}$, where Plasma is the Fire Element, aka Spirit of “The Lord” or *L* power... this is known as ‘sanctification’. The key, also, is ‘consummation’ in the polar relationship.

Table 1 - the Layers of the Force

1 layer <i>P power is...</i>	2 layer <i>“The Polar Field”</i>	3 layer <i>“Samsara”</i>	5 layer <i>“Five phases”</i>	8 layer <i>(see 1 layer)</i>
Causality	Force-Field	Force-field	Force	Force
Flux (evolution)	(PEMF=UAF)	Unified-Aether	Field	Field
Relativity		Plasma-Electromagnetism	Unified	Unified
Conservation		Or simply...	Aether	Aether

²⁹ See: PPPC

³⁰ Work... over-time!

³¹ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

Vibration		Plasma	Gravity ³²	Plasma
Rotation		Electricity	...Where Gravity is	Electricity
Polarity		Magnetism	related to mutual ³³	Magnetism
Resonance		Dynamics	similarity (resonance)	REALITY [realions]

Note - first 4 laws are Laws of Heaven, and second 4 are the Laws of Earth

So one sees that not only is the word *philosophy* related to the *F* power via the sound, and the letter *p*, both literally in English but also mytho-historically, then the entire framework of the concepts are related. Needless to say, Alexander the Great wasn't taught by Aristotle to sit around and achieve nothing, and he exerted himself to his utmost end. Without knowing the rules of power, he failed to maintain it. So we must consistently conceptualize the concepts of "the Force" and Power, within the mimsical framework to keep MIMS to understanding:

- The rules of power
- The curvature of power
- The shi of power
- The maintenance of balance within the philosophæather of MIMS, power, force, energy, and principles.

Plug-N-Play-Platform

What is the point of the MIMS philosophy, or the Philosophæther, for that *matter*, if it remains abstruse and alchemical (that is: an eisegesis of the elite mystics like Newton, Tesla, Edison, Franklin, etc.)? Or, for that matter, contained in these papers, diagrammatica³⁴, mimsy or messy³⁵, and available only to the EPEMC community and the Electric Universe ilk?

Hence the need to combine the four above 'angels' of our æthereal metaphysics with the gift of the late 1990s: "plug-n-play." This is a computerization term that essentially means, "insert and go", describing the ease of use. Therefore, let us look to the *keystone* - the 21st-century 'philosopher's stone' - of the term: the *N* power (numbers). That is, in an ORDA:INED³⁶ relationship (hence: a field) with the data-æther: numericalization of that which is previously kept theorized and abstruse, and only for the high and lofty.

An example of this is the last MESSy about the Spheres of Heaven which took away the power of the flat Earthers, of the mainstream, and of the long-winded rambling conjuring conjecturers³⁷, the right to talk circumspectly about the Heavens, rather than figure out simple things.

- 1) How much power is there?
- 2) Where is it?
- 3) How do we get it?
- 4) What can we do with it?

These are MIMSical matters, and what is pragmatic is what is *E*-fficient: getting results for a mimsical reason. The mimsical reason: to increase human momentum and energy we need more cheap, highly

³² Attraction, alignment, etc.

³³ IE: its form is AME, instead of ætheric, spiritual, imaginative, hyper-dimensional, etc.

³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life

³⁵ [MIMS and MESSy categories](#)

³⁶ [MESS0007: The ORDA Standard](#)

³⁷ https://www.academia.edu/77978879/Theoria_Apophysis_the_Ken_Wheeler_Effect

available energy, and to develop the means to defend ourselves from tyrants and invaders, on or off-planet, and to travel on or off-planet. The Big G makes our plans and our readiness, provides all the framework, and the studies, the science and mimsy, at this time in humanity's course in history, for some **Divine Plan**.

Again, we cannot escape the principled motions of the Heavens, or of the *L* power, which is the seed of all consciousness, itself, in a fractal framework. We tried. And we (humanity) failed. Dark Universe be damned, Big Bang be busted, and space-time be flummoxed... what matters is the entire mimsical rotation of nether/æther energies, washing back and forth from **Space** \rightleftharpoons **Counterspace**. This appears, in the philosophæther to be the very definition of the *A* power (Unified: physics concepts, Truth/Dirac, aether, UAF, PEMF, Tao). This power, at one with Lord and Force, representing a concept of *opti-mysticism*³⁸.

Newton (the good man!) has taken us this far. He may have reincarnated as Tesla to take us that much further. Now we must seek the Force, and accept this Power as the major pivoting axis upon which the symbolic axis-mundi revolves. Upon this cosmic pole motif and archetype rotates all Gnosis, Wisdom, Logos, and the very axle of the power (traditionally a vajra/thunderbolt) is PEM; mostly electromagnetism. That which is moving, is electric. That which is potential is charge and magnetism. That which is barrier is dielectric. That which enables the potential to slosh between the space and SCS³⁹ is dielectricity. Philosophically, it is a conjugated mass; not AME, but realistic. The realion we created - solely for this paper and nowhere else - is therefore completed by the *N* power, and thereby brings about further definition. This is an example of an on-the-fly MIMSy. That is how it must work: in the moment, real, and concentrated for effect.

As for the actual data additive, the numericalization, the author suggests where possible real, ordinals, or even prime numbers (as per R. Ashcroft), and for geometries, simple equations with Platonic solids as a base. For fractals, simplest equations, which have definite use and bend towards asymmetry. For the entire *N* power framework to work, such as with Dual Layer Economics⁴⁰, or the Aether Flexion Wave, the author suggests to the reader to use gaseous plasma as a model for the dæther, and the use of AI or machine learning to 'crunch' through the issues, possibly using cryptocurrencies, which run on electrical math.

Take the MIMS, and make it mathematical, rather than mathemagickal as the mainstream of physics did, and then "everything will turn out all right." The ship will "right" and be "correct," (zheng), and then the Philosophæther can "stand up/right on its own two feet." Etc. No puns intended, just plasmamorphogenic fun.

Platform

What is interesting is the worldwide use of platform pyramids. These may have been sacrificial in some places, but not all. In the manufacture of dark earth soils in Kentucky, they were quite large and probably related to early agriculture⁴¹. In Mexico some were used for sacrifice, but others for giant observation decks with massive mica sheets. In Japan they've been used for sumo wrestling for thousands of years.⁴²

In modern senses, a platform is a "level playing field" where we attempt to make either a) communications arenas or b) systems to enable (as MIMS) the achievement of other things, within a framework of ... whatever it is. Usually software, but not only. In this case, the goal (of course) is to put the MIMS philosophy to work, particularly as it pertains to the **philosophæther**, in the aid of humans, nature, and society (where cooperation works, but if it is harmful, mitigated.)

³⁸ MESS0033: Sir Isaac Newton - the Opti-Mystic

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing_

⁴⁰ See MIMS 1.0 pp 18-21

⁴¹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

⁴² https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

References

1. "How to Create a MIMS," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How_to_Create_a_MIMS
2. "MESS0008: Induction vs. Deduction in MIMS," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87578070/MESS0008_MIMS_2_9_Induction_or_intuitive_MIMS_Creation_vs_Deductive_reductive_or_empirical_methods
3. "Sherlock Holmes: Pioneer in Forensic Science". Encyclopedia Britannica. J. O'Brien, 2014, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sherlock-Holmes-Pioneer-in-Forensic-Science-1976713>
4. "MIMS 1.12 - Self-Consistency of the "Big G" Diagram," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
5. "Membranous Interface of Material & Spiritual," (EPEMC) Gateway/The Pulse," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims>
6. "Acronyms, Sf. R. Careaga, https://docs.google.com/document/d/1q92mAAOhqYiK1f6QQuYQ2MjXYOrgPwi3SY_heDLzio8/edit
7. "MESS0017: AFW - Using Fisheye and Pinch lens to discern Pixelation Adaptation," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88285198/MESS0017_AFW_Using_Fish_eye_and_Pinch_lens_to_discern_Pixelation_Adaptation
8. "Structure of the Uni-Multiverse; pre-EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC
9. "MIMS 2.2.1.1-3: The Threefold Science," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>
10. "MIMS & Shi," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi
11. "MESS0007 - MIMS 2.101: The ORDA Standard," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard
12. "Explication of the Versatility of the "Big G" diagram in MIMS 1.0," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0
13. "Original Tao: Inward Training (Nei-yeh) and the Foundations of Taoist Mysticism (Translations from the Asian Classics)," Amazon, H. Roth, 2004, <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652/>
14. "The Primo Vascular System as a New Anatomical System," ScienceDirect/Journal of Acupuncture and Meridian Studies Volume 6, M. Stefanov et al, 2013, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2005290113002082>
15. "Charge Distribution Networks (CDN) as Meridians Utilizing conductivity as replacement 'structure' for meridians; comparison with neural, muscular, and fascial models, ResearchGate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models
16. "MESS0018: GEO 2.2 -Electrogeology evidence in macrolytic magnetic and gravitic field anomalies in VA, NC, and KY.," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88366256/MESS0018_GEO_2_2_Electrogeology_evidence_in_macrolytic_magnetic_and_gravitic_field_anomalies_in_VA_NC_and_KY
17. "MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88844488/MESS0023_MET_2_22_The_Spheres_of_Heaven
18. "Uchell, the High Lord, and Shang Di," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38744706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di
19. "Enki & The World Order," Sf. R. Careaga, 2020, https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njK-K-trnbGGjq5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit#slide=id.p
20. "Ashes of Atlantis - part 1," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1
21. "MESS0014 - Gravity as a Newtonian PEMF; Resonance and Conservation," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/87940630/MESS0014_Gravity_as_a_Newtonian_PEMF_Resonance_and_Conservation
22. "MESS0016 - Newtonian Mechanics, Kinetics, and Sound in an Electrodynamics Model; or creating a MOND2 on the basis of the Force for Plasma-Electromagnetic Dynamics (PEMD)," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88245613/MESS0016_Newtonian_Mechanics_Kinetics_and_Sound_in_an_Electrodynamics_Model_or_creating_a_MOND2_on_the_basis_of_the_Force_for_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Dynamics_PEMD
23. "Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis
24. "MIMS 2.2.5.2 - The Five "forces" that Influence Life," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life
25. "MIMS and MESSy categories" Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://docs.google.com/document/d/1F_SB711Kc_gqcQtg9lpAM799WR4ulU-J8VpMU1IT3YQ/edit
26. "Theoria Apophasis: the Ken Wheeler Effect," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/77978879/Theoria_Apophasis_the_Ken_Wheeler_Effect
27. "MESS0033: Sir Isaac Newton - the Opti-Mystic," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga ^
28. "Something from "Nothing" Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/63382042/Something_from_Nothing
29. "Great Pyramids of Kentucky - Final," ResearchGate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final
30. "Sumo: Ancient Ritual to the Thunder God," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God